

Determinant Analysis to Improve Tourist Satisfaction at Travel Honey Bee Scout Park

Witri Nur April Aini

Master of Management, Faculty of Economics and Business
 Mercu Buana University
 Jakarta, Indonesia

Wahyu Hari Haji

Master of Management, Faculty of Economics and Business
 Mercu Buana University
 Jakarta, Indonesia

Abstract:- The purpose of this study aims to analyze the important factors to increase tourist satisfaction at Travel Honey Bee Scout Park. Questionnaires were given to tourists who have visited Beehive Tourism Park for the last five years, obtained 210 respondents using a purposive sampling technique. The analytical method used in this study is Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). Data processed with SmartPLS 3.0. The results confirm that; e-WOM and Travel Motivation have a positive but not significant effect on visiting decisions. Tourist Attraction has a positive and significant effect on visiting decisions; e-WOM and Travel Motivation have a positive and insignificant effect on tourist satisfaction; Tourist Attraction has a positive and significant effect on tourist satisfaction; Visiting Decisions have a positive and significant impact on Tourist Satisfaction. Tourist Attraction is the variable that has the greatest influence on Tourist Satisfaction.

Keywords:- E-WOM, Travel Motivation, Tourist Attraction, Visiting Decisions, Tourist Satisfaction, Bee Tourism Park.

I. INTRODUCTION

Tourism itself is defined as tourism activities supported by various facilities and services provided by the community, entrepreneurs and local governments (UU No. 10/2009 in Chapter I). The tourism sector ranks second in contributing to the country's foreign exchange after palm oil. The Special Capital Region of Jakarta as the nation's capital has the slogan "Enjoy Jakarta" as city branding. It is hoped that with this slogan people from various countries visiting Indonesia can recognize Jakarta apart from being the nation's capital as well as a must-visit tourist destination. One of the many tourist destinations in DKI Jakarta is the Travel Honey Bee Scout Park, which is located in the Cibubur area, East Jakarta.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, tourism activities in Indonesia experienced a very significant decline, so that managers of tourist attractions had to take appropriate actions so that they could survive until the pandemic was declared over, therefore the Travel Honey Bee Scout Park management needed to implement a strategy. -a new strategy to continue to be able to attract local and foreign tourists in accordance with government policies, namely the new normal.

Based on internal data, the Travel Honey Bee Scout Park shows a significant decrease in the number of visits by local and foreign tourists due to the impact of COVID-19.

Table 1. Data On Tourist Visit Travel Honey Bee Scout Park

Month	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
January	639	550	756	2,879	1,550
February	1,248	1,205	5,395	5,308	3,237
March	2,474	1,429	5,144	5,801	828
April	1,296	1,066	4,632	4,289	0
May	1,359	1,288	2,617	1,315	0
June	273	100	969	2,749	0
July	0	475	3,158	3,536	127
August	119	173	1,445	1015	142
Sept	1,233	1,401	3,636	3,635	61
October	1,378	3,482	9,488	7,214	44
November	2,172	2,612	8,131	6,188	341
December	2,599	1870	7,479	4,958	154
Amount	14,790	15,651	52,850	48,887	6,484

Source: Internal Data, processed (2021)

In table 1 above, we can see that the beginning of the decline in the number of tourists visiting the Pramuka Honey Bee Tourism Park occurred in March, which was the month when the COVID-19 pandemic spread to Indonesia. The very significant reduction in the number of visits made the company's revenue decrease. The measure of the success of a tourist attraction is the growth in the number of tourists visiting the tourist attraction. When viewed from the significant decline in the number of visitors in 2020 compared to the previous year, this is of course based on the decisions taken by tourists in determining tourist destinations. Based on journal reviews from previous studies, there are several factors that can influence the decision to visit tourists. These factors include the location of tourist attractions, travel motivation, destination image, service quality, attractiveness, price, e-wom and perceived value. The author conducted a pre-survey of 30 respondents who were at Bee Tourism Park aged at least 16 years to find out what factors are considered by tourists in deciding to visit the Lebah Tourism Park. The results of the top three pre-survey revealed that the factors influencing the decision to visit Bee Tourism Park tourists were e-WOM of 100%, followed by attractiveness of 97%, travel motivation of 93%. Tourist satisfaction at the Bee Tourism Park needs to be considered and is one of the aspects that must be examined to

find solutions to the problem of the decreasing number of tourists coming to the Bee Tourism Park. The theory presented by Mathieson and Wall (1982) in Kristiutami (2017) states that the decision to choose a tourist object is basically a purchase decision, namely spending money to get satisfaction. That is, the satisfaction obtained by tourists will directly be influenced by the decision to visit.

The next factor is positive reviews from tourists about tourist destinations that can encourage tourists to decide to visit. Research conducted by Sari and Pangestuti (2018) shows that e-WOM has a positive and significant effect on visiting decisions. The results of research by Widyanto, et al (2017) also show that the effect of e-WOM on visiting decisions is significant, one can find out the conditions and attractions through information and suggestions received through social media so that they can make decisions about visiting these attractions.

Based on these factors, a pre-survey was carried out on 30 respondents to find out what factors are considered by tourists to visit the Bee Tourism Park.

II. LITERATURE REVIEWS

A. Marketing Management

Marketing is an activity that aims to satisfy the needs and desires of customers through exchange processes and parties with an interest in the company (Sunyoto, 2014:18). According to Kotler and Keller (2017: 6) marketing management is, "The art and science of choosing target markets and getting, keeping, and growing superior customers".

B. Tourism Destinations

According to Law No. 10 of 2009 tourism destinations are "Geographical areas that are in one or more administrative areas in which there are tourist attractions, tourism facilities, accessibility, and communities that are interrelated and complement the realization of tourism".

C. Tourism Marketing

According to Liga and Vanny (2015: 115) tourism marketing is, "A system that coordinates with each other to carry out various policies for tourism industry group companies, whether owned by individuals or private or government agencies, whether local, regional, national or international to achieve customer satisfaction. traveler.

D. Electronic Word of Mouth

Electronic word of mouth is a positive or negative statement made by a potential customer or former customer about a product or company, which is intended for many people or institutions via the internet (Litving et al., 2004 in Jalilvand, 2012). In this study, researchers used five dimensions of e-Wom that matched the research. This is the same as research conducted by Yudhistira (2018) regarding the effects of e-WOM on visiting decisions. The five dimensions are:

- Assistance Platforms
- Concern for others
- Expressing Positive
- Economic Incentives
- Helping the Company

E. Travel Motivation

Travel Motivation is the drive that makes a person make the decision to travel. In addition, travel motivation is defined as a need that requires a person to act in a certain way to achieve the desired satisfaction and the reasons behind why people travel or choose tourist destinations (Beard and Ragheb, 1983 in Baniya and Paudel, 2016).

Furthermore, Beard and Ragheb (1983) in Baniya (2016) based on Maslow's model state four motivational needs which are also the basis of the motivational comfort scale, namely:

- Intellectual Component
- Social Component
- Competence of Acquiring Skills
- The Stimulus Avoidance Component

F. Tourist attraction

Heath and Wall (1992) in Syahrul (2015) stated that the factors that determine success in developing a tourist destination include three factors, namely:

- Tourist Attraction
- Amenity
- Accessibilities

G. Visit Decision

Kotler and Keller (2017: 235) explain that in general consumers will experience a five-stage process before making a decision which includes problem recognition, information search, evaluation of alternatives, purchase decisions, and post-purchase behavior.

H. Tourist Satisfaction

Tourist satisfaction is the result of a comparison between expectations and experiences at the destination and if visitors are satisfied with the results of a comparison between experience and expectations, then tourists are satisfied with the destination. Otherwise, visitors will not be satisfied (Li et al., 2016).

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The design of the research conducted is causal research. The population of this study were tourists who had traveled to the Travel Honey Bee Scout Park for the last five years, by collecting samples using the purposive sampling method, namely taking samples with certain criteria. According to Hair et al in Ghozali and Fuad (2014: 13) determine the number of representative samples by recommending 5-10 times the number of manifest variables used in the study. Thus the minimum sample size in this study is 30 indicators multiplied by 7 (30×7) = 210 respondents.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data obtained in this study is by distributing questionnaires targeted at tourists who have been to the Bee Tourism Park for the last 5 years. A total of 210 questionnaires were used for data analysis samples. Then the data collected was then analyzed descriptively and quantitatively. Descriptive analysis was carried out with the help of the Microsoft Excel program to describe the variables e-WOM, Travel Motivation, Tourist Attractiveness Visit Decision and Tourist Satisfaction. Meanwhile, quantitative analysis was carried out using the PLS (Partial Least Square) method to determine the influence of e-WOM, Travel motivation, Tourist Attraction, Visit Decision and Tourist Satisfaction.

If seen from table 2, it shows that the number of male and female tourists who come to visit the Bee Tourism Park is only slightly different. The result is a higher percentage of male tourists. The following is a thorough description of the descriptive respondents based on the questionnaire answers.

Table 2 Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristics	Total	Percentage (%)	
Gender	Man	115	54.8%
	Woman	95	45.2%
	Total	210	100%
Age	<20 Years	6	2.9%
	21-38 Years	91	43.3%
	39-50 Years	90	42.9%
	51-69 Years	23	10.9%
	Total	210	100%
Education	SMA/Equivalent	64	30.5%
	Diploma	13	6.2%
	Total	210	100%
Expenses/month	<1 Million	17	8.1%
	1-3 Million	56	26.7%
	Total	210	100%

Source: Results of data processing (2021)

Tourists who visit the Bee Tourism Park are mostly dominated by families, because the Bee Tourism Park is an educational as well as recreational tourist spot for families. This can be seen from the percentage of visitors to the Bee Tourism Park. The Bee Tourism Park is also visited by many tourists who have spending more than 3 million each month. Therefore, it is better if the marketing of the Honeycomb Tourism Park focuses on this segment as the main target in developing strategies in an effort to increase the number of tourists at Travel Honey Bee Scout Park.

A. Results of Partial Least Square Analysis

To evaluate the model formed in this study, several tests were carried out to answer whether the latent variables studied were e-WOM, Travel Motivation, Tourist Attractiveness, Visit Decision and Tourist Satisfaction can consistently be explained precisely by each construct. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out 2 (two) tests, namely the measurement model test (Outer Model) and the structural model test (Inner Model). The data processing technique in this study uses the SEM method based on Partial Least Square (PLS) where the data processing uses the SmartPLS 3.3.3 program. The Outer Model schematic analyzed using the PLS-Algorithm method is presented in Figure 1 below.

Source: SmartPLS Processing Results (2021)

The figure above presents the loading factor values of each indicator, the path coefficient values and the R-Square values. The scheme of the Inner Model model analyzed through the PLS-Bootstrapping method is presented in Figure 3.2 below:

Fig 2 below presents data regarding t-statistics and p-values from the interaction of one variable to another.

Source: SmartPLS Processing Results (2021)

➤ *Outer Model*

The manifest variables in the study include the following:

- The e-WOM latent variable (X1) is measured by 9 observed variables, namely X1.1, X1.2, X1.3, X1.4, X1.5, X1.6, X1.7, X1.8 and X1.9
- The latent variable Travel Motivation (X2) is measured by 6 observed variables, namely X2.1, X2.2, X2.3, X2.4, X2.5, and X2.6
- Attractiveness latent variable (X3) is measured by 7 observed variables, namely X3.1, X3.2, X3.3, X3.4, X3.5, X3.6, and X3.7
- The visiting decision latent variable (Z) is measured by 4 observed variables, namely Z1, Z2, Z3 and Z4
- The latent variable Tourist Satisfaction (Y) is measured by 4 observed variables, namely Y1, Y2, Y3 and Y4

➤ *Inner Model*

The latent variable Visit Decision (Z) is influenced by the latent variable e-WOM (X1), Travel Motivaton (X2), Attractiveness (X3). The latent variable Tourist Satisfaction (Y) is influenced by the latent variable e-WOM (X1), Travel Motivaton (X2), Attractiveness (X3) and the latent variable Tourist Satisfaction (Y).

B. Measurement Model Test Results (outer model)

Then an evaluation is carried out regarding the validity and reliability of the indicators as described below:

➤ *Validation Test*

Testing the validity of this research model is by analyzing construct validity. Construct validity shows how well the results obtained from the use of a measurement match the theories used to define a construct. Construct validity consists of convergent validity and discriminant validity.

• *Convergent Validity*

Convergent validity aims to determine the validity of each relationship between indicators and constructs or latent variables. To test convergent validity, factor loading values are used. An indicator is declared to meet convergent validity which is said to be high or in the good category if the outer loading value is > 0.70. However, according to Chin, quoted by Ghozali (2015: 74), an outer loading value between 0.5 and 0.6 is considered sufficient to meet the requirements of convergent validity. By looking at the output results of the correlation between the indicators and their constructs as shown in the table below:

Table 3 Convergent Validity Test Results

Measurement Models			
Latent Variable	Indicator Code	Outer Loading ≥ 0.70	Information
E-WOM (X1)	EWOM1	0.938	Valid
	EWOM2	0.924	Valid
	EWOM3	0.759	Valid
	EWOM4	0.731	Valid
	EWOM5	0.962	Valid
	EWOM6	0.955	Valid
	EWOM7	0.965	Valid
	EWOM8	0.967	Valid
	EWOM9	0.968	Valid
Travel Motivation (X2)	TM1	0.879	Valid
	TM2	0.886	Valid
	TM3	0.581	Invalid
	TM4	0.764	Valid
	TM5	0.428	Invalid
	TM6	0.428	Invalid
Attractiveness (X3)	DT1	0.667	Invalid
	DT2	0.686	Invalid
	DT3	0.778	Valid
	DT4	0.775	Valid
	DT5	0.832	Valid
	DT6	0.799	Valid
	DT7	0.742	Valid
Visit Decision (Z)	KB1	0.672	Invalid
	KB2	0.785	Valid
	KB3	0.840	Valid
	KB4	0.836	Valid
Tourist Satisfaction (Y)	KW1	0.934	Valid
	KW2	0.939	Valid
	KW3	0.730	Valid
	KW4	0.870	Valid

Source: SmartPLS Output Data Processed Results (2021)

Based on table 3 above, the results of the convergent validity test show that there are several indicators that do not meet the requirements of convergent validity because they have a loading factor value of less than 0.70 so that they are declared invalid. Therefore, re-estimation was carried out by removing these indicators from the construct model. Modification of convergent validity can be seen in the table below:

Table 4 Convergent Validity Test Results (Modification)

Measurement Models			
Latent Variable	Indicator Code	Outer Loading ≥ 0.70	Information
Travel Motivation (X2)	TM1	0.970	Valid
	TM2	0.973	Valid
	TM4	0.823	Valid
E-WOM (X1)	EWOM1	0.934	Valid
	EWOM2	0.920	Valid
	EWOM3	0.769	Valid
	EWOM4	0.742	Valid
	EWOM5	0.959	Valid
	EWOM6	0.951	Valid
	EWOM7	0.961	Valid
	EWOM8	0.963	Valid
	EWOM9	0.964	Valid
Attractiveness (X3)	DT3	0.754	Valid
	DT4	0.785	Valid
	DT5	0.828	Valid
	DT6	0.851	Valid
	DT7	0.811	Valid
Visit Decision (Y)	KB2	0.742	Valid
	KB3	0.884	Valid
	KB4	0.877	Valid
Tourist Satisfaction (Z)	KW1	0.936	Valid
	KW2	0.940	Valid
	KW3	0.726	Valid
	KW4	0.870	Valid

Source: SmartPLS Output Data Processed Results (2021)

Based on the loading factor values in table 4 above, the data shows that all loading factor values have given the value above the suggested value of 0.70. So that the indicators used in this study are valid or have met the requirements of convergent validity. Thus the analysis can be continued with the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) Test.

Table 5 Average Variance Extracted (AVE) Test Results

Variable	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Information
e-WOM	0.821	Valid
Travel Motivation	0.860	Valid
Attractiveness	0.663	Valid
Visit Decision	1,000	Valid
Tourist Satisfaction	0.990	Valid

Source: SmartPLS Processing Results (2021)

In this study, the AVE value of each construct was ≥ 0.50 so that there were no problems and met the Convergent Validity standard. Thus, the entire construct can be declared valid and can be continued with Discriminant Validity testing.

• *Discriminant Validity*

The discriminant validity test can be seen in the cross loading between the indicator and the construct. According to Ghazali (2015: 39) An indicator is declared valid or declared to meet discriminant validity if the cross loading value of the

indicator on the variable is the largest compared to other variables, as shown in Table 6 below:

Table 6 Discriminant Validity Test Results (Cross Loadings)

Indicator	e-WOM	Travel Motivation	Attractiveness	Visit Decision	Tourist Satisfaction
EWOM1	0.934	0.404	0.465	0.363	0.365
EWOM2	0.920	0.427	0.498	0.472	0.385
EWOM3	0.770	0.450	0.500	0.433	0.477
EWOM4	0.743	0.416	0.477	0.406	0.449
EWOM5	0.959	0.426	0.431	0.342	0.343
EWOM6	0.951	0.412	0.419	0.333	0.332
EWOM7	0.961	0.397	0.458	0.347	0.361
EWOM8	0.963	0.385	0.462	0.350	0.368
EWOM9	0.964	0.392	0.469	0.357	0.370
TM1	0.462	0.970	0.484	0.384	0.387
TM2	0.462	0.973	0.477	0.381	0.385
TM4	0.339	0.824	0.361	0.300	0.296
DT3	0.413	0.357	0.754	0.434	0.483
DT4	0.360	0.384	0.787	0.452	0.487
DT5	0.386	0.393	0.831	0.563	0.570
DT6	0.500	0.397	0.849	0.470	0.506
DT7	0.437	0.406	0.809	0.476	0.515
KB3	0.345	0.327	0.588	0.926	0.865
KB4	0.413	0.384	0.502	0.905	0.757
KW1	0.385	0.367	0.617	0.848	0.963
KW2	0.389	0.350	0.621	0.841	0.966
KW4	0.433	0.367	0.537	0.789	0.856

Source: SmartPLS Processing Results (2021)

C. *Structural Model Tester (Inner Model)*

Structural model analysis is carried out with the aim of ensuring that the structural model built is robust and accurate. Structural model analysis in PLS is evaluated using R² for the dependent construct, and the path coefficient values or t-values of each path for the significance test between constructs in the structural model. The R² value is used to measure the level of variation in the independent variable changes to the dependent variable. The higher the R² value means the better the prediction model of the proposed research model.

D. *Hypothesis Tester*

Based on the Path Coefficient Test, if the Path Coefficient value is < 0 then the direction of the relationship is negative, whereas if > 0 then the direction of the relationship is positive. While the t-statistic tests the level of significance of the effect of the relationship, if the t-statistic value with a significance level of 5% has a t-table value > 1.96 then the direction of the relationship is significant (Vinci et al, 2010). Furthermore, if the p-value < 0.05 , there is influence between the independent variables and the dependent variable.

The following are the results of hypothesis testing obtained in the study as presented in table 7 below.

Table 7 Hypothesis Results

No.	hypothesis	Results		Conclusion
		Coefficient	T Statistics	
H1	<i>e-WOM</i> -> Visit Decision	0.111	1,521	Rejected because it is not significant
H2	Travel motivation -> Decisions Visit	0.099	1.419	Rejected because not significant
H3	Tourist Attraction -> Decision Visit	0.493	7,073	Be accepted
H4	<i>e-WOM</i> -> Tourist Satisfaction	0.030	0.554	Rejected because not significant
H5	Travel motivation-> Satisfaction Traveler	0.003	0.103	Rejected because not significant
H6	Tourist Attraction -> Satisfaction Traveler	0.154	2,726	Be accepted
H7	Visit Decision -> Tourist Satisfaction	0.786	11,975	Be accepted
H8	<i>e-WOM</i> towards satisfaction tourists through visiting decisions	0.087	1,466	Rejected because it is not significant
H9	Travel motivationon tourist satisfaction through Visit decision	0.078	1,437	Rejected because it is not significant
H10	Tourist Attraction to tourist satisfaction through Visit decision	0.387	7,126	Be accepted

Source: SmartPLS Output Data Processed Results (2021)

V. CONCLUSION

A. Conclusion

Based on the results of the research and discussion that was carried out in the previous chapter, the factors that are considered to increase tourists at Travel Honey Bee Scout Park. Then it can be concluded as follows:

- *e-WOM* positive but not significant effect on the decision to visit.
- *Travel motivation* positive but not significant effect on the decision to visit.
- Tourist attraction has a positive and significant effect on visiting decisions. Tourist attraction is very dominant on the decision to visit.
- *e-WOM* positive and insignificant effect on tourist satisfaction. *e-WOM* has no influence on tourist satisfaction.
- *Travel motivation* positive but not significant effect on tourist satisfaction.
- Tourist attraction has a positive and significant effect on tourist satisfaction.
- The decision to visit has a positive and significant effect on tourist satisfaction.
- *e-WOM* has a positive but not significant effect on tourist satisfaction through visiting decisions.
- *Travel motivation* has a positive but not significant effect on tourist satisfaction through visiting decisions.
- Tourist attraction has a positive and significant effect on tourist satisfaction through visiting decisions.

B. Suggestions

➤ Advice for Academics

This research still has limitations in a number of ways that have not yet been discussed on the topic of this research and are expected to be continued for further research. Some of the things that could become material for further research are:

- Limited research time and government policies related to the operational time of tourist attractions during the Covid-

19 pandemic caused more research samples to be obtained from tourist respondents who live in Jakarta

- Based on the research results, it is highly recommended for academics and future researchers to test other research variables to increase the generalization of research findings

The template is designed so that author affiliations are not repeated each time for multiple authors of the same affiliation. Please keep your affiliations as succinct as possible (for example, do not differentiate between departments of the same organization). This template was designed for two affiliates.

➤ Suggestions for the Management of Bee Tourism Parks

Based on the results of the analysis in the previous chapter, several things that can be suggested to increase the number of tourist visits are as follows:

Based on the results of hypothesis testing, the variable tourist attraction has the most or the greatest influence on tourist satisfaction. Therefore, the management is expected to continue to improve and add facilities that can support tourists to visit the Lebah Tourism Park. Such as a safer children's play area, more complete food restaurants and more adequate facilities for worship. Existing educational tour packages can be developed and improved again so that the educational tourism label attached to the Bee Tourism Park remains a special attraction. Goa facilities that already exist and are unique in themselves can be put to better use by beautifying the surrounding environment.

Next is the travel motivation factor because it has the second biggest influence on tourist satisfaction. These suggestions are based on the value of the loading factor which has the highest or closest value to the travel motivation variable. So that the advice that can be given by company management related to group educational tours is not only for schools but other communities who want to travel while strengthening family relationships. Facilities for shelter for tourists are given more attention considering that the area is an open nature area. So that the Tourism Park becomes a tourist

spot that many families and communities go to to strengthen relationships and also a place to escape from the daily routine.

The e-WOM variable has no influence on tourist satisfaction. This is due to the lack of promotion by the Bee Tourism Park. In the digital era, promotion can be done through social media, but Taman Wisata Lebah has not used it properly. Through this promotion, a lot of information can be provided starting from price packages, what activities are carried out, existing facilities and also access to destination locations. Of course, this should be of particular concern to the management of the Bee Tourism Park. Not only social media, promotion through conventional means can still be done as a form of effort such as printing brochures and distributing them to potential places. The active role of existing employees will also influence, especially in conveying information that prospective tourists want to know.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Adisaputro, Gunawan. (2014). Marketing Management Analysis For Marketing Strategy Design. Second printing. YKPN College of Management. Yogyakarta.
- [2]. Anggono, AJ and Sunarti. (2018). "The Influence of Price and Word of Mouth on Visiting Decisions (Survey of Visitors to Paragliding Tourism, Batu City)". Journal of Business Administration (JAB). Vol. 61 No. 3.
- [3]. Ariani, ZR and Wandebori, H. (2016). "The Influence of Product Attributes of Tourism and Electronic Word of Mouth (eWOM) on the Decision on Visiting Parang Ijo Waterfall in Karanganyar Region, Central Java".
- [4]. Aprilia, ER, Sunarti. and Pangestuti, E. (2017). "The Influence of Tourist Attractions and Service Facilities on Tourist Satisfaction at Balekambang Beach, Malang Regency". Journal of Business Administration. Vol. 51 No. 2.
- [5]. Bania, Rojan. and Paudel, Kirtika. (2016). "An Analysis of Push and Pull Travel Motivations of Domestic Tourists in Nepal". Journal of Management and Development Studies, Vol. 27, pp. 16-30.
- [6]. Bataineh, AQ (2015). "The Impact of Perceived e-WOM on Purchase Intention: The Mediating Role of Corporate Image". International Journal of Marketing Studies. Vol. 7 No. 1 ISSN 1918-719X.
- [7]. Boniface, B., Cooper, R. and Cooper, C. (2016). Worldwide Destinations the Geography of Travel and Tourism. 7th Edition. Oxons. New York
- [8]. Chandra, MN (2019). "The Influence of Customer Value, Perceived Enjoyment and Online Word of Mouth on the Purchase Decision of Local Tourists to Bali". AGORA. Vol. 7 No. 1.
- [9]. Ghozali, Imam. (2017). Structural Equation Model Concepts and Applications with the AMOS 24 Update Bayesian SEM Program. Diponegoro University Publishing Agency. Semarang.
- [10]. Ghozali, Imam and Fuad. (2014). Structural Equation Modeling Theory, Concepts and Applications with Programs. LISREL 9.10. Issue 4. Diponegoro University Publishing Agency. Semarang
- [11]. Setyaningsih, S. and Murwatiningsih. (2017). "The Influence of Motivation, Promotion and Destination Image on Visitor Satisfaction Through Visitor Decisions. Management Analysis Journal. ISSN 2252-6552.
- [12]. Siyoto, Sandu. and Sodik, Ali. (2015). Basic Research Methodology. Literacy Media Publishing. Yogyakarta.
- [13]. Safitasari, C and Maftukhah. I. (2017). "The Influence of Service Quality, Promotion and Destination Image on Satisfaction Through Visitor Decisions". Management Analysis Journal. ISSN 2252-6552.